

Cure Rate Model in Survival Analysis Using Cubic Transmuted Dagum Distribution

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ABSTRACT:

The study made an attempt to extend the application of Dagum distribution to biostatistics from the conventional use in analysing income distribution, which they added a parameter to the distribution and called it transmuted Dagum distribution, [10]. [6] added a parameter λ to the transmuted Dagum distribution and called it cubic transmuted Dagum distribution. An attempt was made in this paper to use cubic transmuted Dagum distribution to model a real life data and use it to develop a cure model. The method of maximum likelihood estimate was used to estimate the parameters of the model and AIC and BIC was used to test to best of fit of the model and was discovered that the cubic transmuted Dagum fits the cure model better than its previous distribution.

Keywords: Survival Analysis, Cure Model, Dagum Distribution.

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INTRODUCTION

In many biological and medical studies, the main outcome under assessment is the time to an event of interest. The generic name for the time is *survival time*, although it may be applied to the time 'survived' from complete remission to relapse or progression as equally as to the time from diagnosis to death.

Survival analysis is a branch of Statistics which deals with the analysis of expected duration of time until one or more event(s) happen, such as death in biological organisms, failure in mechanical systems, and event history analysis in History or Sociology etc, [1]. This branch of empirical science entails gathering and analyzing data on time until failure or death, is called survival analysis. It includes a variety of specific type of data analysis including "life table analysis," "time to failure" methods, and "time to death" analysis. Reliability methods and life contingencies are based on the same fundamental principles of survival analysis.

In realizing the importance of this aspect of Statistics, there has been a phenomenal increase in the usage of survival analysis, and in a quest for a better method of exploring survival function, many researchers have resorted to applying different probability distributions in fitting survival data. The

question is, “Can we still have other distribution that can be used as an improvement on the existing distributions?”

According to [2], Survival analysis is a useful statistical technique for answering questions that deal with the duration of events like, “how long will the patient live?” or “how much has the victim’s life been shortened?” An exact answer is not possible to either question, and only an answer as a statistical probability can be obtained. A statistical answer entails an average or “expected value” with an associated level of uncertainty.

A recent development in survival analysis is the introduction of the cure models in survival analysis. A common assumption in survival data analysis is that all of the study subjects will eventually experience the event of interest if they are followed long enough. However, in reality, the event may not occur with some subjects, even after a very long period of time. For example, in clinical trials, there exist a proportion of subjects who will not experience such an event. In this case, the patients are not censored in the traditional sense and are hence confidently assumed to be cured. Therefore, traditional survival models such as the Cox proportional hazard model or the accelerated failure time are not appropriate for such cured subjects. Consequently, cure models have been developed for manipulation and analyzing survival data with cure fraction.

When the subjects under study do not experience the event of interest; they are considered to be ‘cured’. The population is thus a mixture of two subpopulations: the one of cured subjects, and the one of ‘susceptible’ subjects. When covariates are present, a so-called mixture cure model can be used to model the conditional survival function of the population. It depends on two components: the probability of being cured and the conditional survival function of the susceptible subjects. Cure models are a popular topic within statistical literature but are not as widely known in the clinical literature. Many patients of cancer can be long-term survivors of the disease, and cure models can be a useful tool to analyze and describe such ailment in survival data [3].

Progress in the treatment of cancer led to a spate of statistical research to develop cure models such [4]. Many analysis of such survival data are based on overall survival. No patient can be cured of death, so in these situations, cure models can be used to model long-term survivors rather than cured patients. Cure models can be used to investigate the heterogeneity between patients with ailment who are long-term survivor and those who are not. A straightforward way to identify whether a particular data set might have a subset of long-term survivors is to look at the survival curve. If the survival curve has a plateau at the end of the study, a cure model may be an appropriate and useful way to analyze the data. Standard parametric theory assumes that, if followed for a long enough period, all individuals/components will eventually die/fail. Cure models relax this assumption when it is appropriate to do so. These models assume that some proportion of the individuals/components are ‘cured’ of the event of interest, that is, the event will not occur for them. ‘Cure’ is said to occur when the event of interest returns to the same level as that expected in the general population. This cure proportion is then incorporated into the log-likelihood equation. The so called ‘cure’ model takes its name from the fact that it accounts for those who have reached a population level of ‘cure [5].

Probability distributions are being used in many areas of life. The application of statistical tools, depends upon the underlying probability model of the data. As a result huge numbers of probability distributions are being developed to handle survival data and cure models. However, there still remains large numbers of practical problems that do not follow any of the standard probability distributions. So, developing the new form of the probability distributions is very much common in statistical theory, and many statistical distributions have been developed which are very useful in describing and predicting real-world phenomena.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

According to [6], the survival function of a Cubic transmuted Dagum distribution is the probability function that a system or an individual will survive beyond a given time. Mathematically, survival function is given by:

$S(x) = 1 - F(x)$ where $F(x)$ is the cdf of the cubic transmuted distribution given as:

$$S_1(x) = 1 - \left\{ (1 - \lambda)(1 + \alpha x^{-\theta})^{-\beta} + 3\lambda[(1 + \alpha x^{-\theta})^{-\beta}]^2 - 2\lambda[(1 + \alpha x^{-\theta})^{-\beta}]^3 \right\}$$

$$S_1(x) = 1 - (1 - \lambda)(1 + \alpha x^{-\theta})^{-\beta} - 3\lambda(1 + \alpha x^{-\theta})^{-2\beta} + 2\lambda(1 + \alpha x^{-\theta})^{-3\beta}$$

According to [7], the standard cure model is given as $S(x) = [p_1 + (1 - p_1)S_1(x)]$. substituting $S_1(x)$ of the cubic transmuted Dagum distribution into the standard cure model to give the cure rate model of cubic transmuted Dagum distribution.

The Maximum Likelihood Estimation

According to [8], the maximum likelihood estimation can be used to estimate parameters of a model. The mixture cure model is given as:

$$L = \prod_{j=1}^m [(1 - p)f_0(t)]^{\sigma_j} [p(1 - p)s_0(t)]^{1 - \sigma_j}$$

Also the Mixture Cure model has a Bounded Cumulative Hazard (BCH) model. This method was suggested by Yakovlev et al. as cited by [9], using the mixture model, the log likelihood function is given by

$$L_i = \{[f_1(x)]^{\delta_i} [S_1(x)]^{1 - \delta_i}\} = \{(1 - p)f_1(x)]^{\delta_i} [p + (1 - p)S_1(x)]^{1 - \delta_i}\} \quad (1)$$

Where

δ_i is the censored data while $1 - \delta_i$ is the uncensored data

$$f_1(x) = \alpha\theta\beta x^{-\theta-1} \left\{ (1 + \alpha x^{-\theta})^{-\beta-1} [1 - \lambda + 6\lambda](1 + \alpha x^{-\theta})^{-\beta} - 6\lambda[(1 + \alpha x^{-\theta})^{-\beta}]^2 \right\} \quad (2)$$

and

$$S_1(x) = 1 - \left\{ (1 - \lambda)(1 + \alpha x^{-\theta})^{-\beta} + 3\lambda[(1 + \alpha x^{-\theta})^{-\beta}]^2 - 2\lambda[(1 + \alpha x^{-\theta})^{-\beta}]^3 \right\} \quad (3)$$

Taking the natural logarithm of L_i

$$\log_e L_i = \delta_i \ln\{(1 - p)f_1(x)\} + (1 - \delta_i) \ln\{p + (1 - p)S_1(x)\}$$

By substitution (3) and (2) into (1)

$$\log_e L_i = \delta_i \ln\left\{ (1 - p) \left[\alpha\theta\beta x^{-\theta-1} \left\{ (1 + \alpha x^{-\theta})^{-\beta-1} [1 - \lambda + 6\lambda](1 + \alpha x^{-\theta})^{-\beta} - 6\lambda[(1 + \alpha x^{-\theta})^{-\beta}]^2 \right\} \right] \right\} + (1 - \delta_i) \ln\left\{ p + (1 - p) \left[1 - (1 - \lambda)(1 + \alpha x^{-\theta})^{-\beta} - 3\lambda(1 + \alpha x^{-\theta})^{-2\beta} + 2\lambda(1 + \alpha x^{-\theta})^{-3\beta} \right] \right\} \quad (4)$$

Simplifying (4)

$$\log_e L_i = \{-(\theta + 1)(1 - p)\alpha\theta\beta\delta_i \ln x - (\beta + 1)\ln(1 + \alpha x^{-\theta}) - \beta \ln([1 - \lambda + 6\lambda](1 + \alpha x^{-\theta})) + 12\lambda\beta^2 \ln((1 + \alpha x^{-\theta})) + (1 - \delta_i) \ln(p + (1 - p)) + (1 - \delta_i)(1 - (1 - \lambda)) - (1 - p)\beta \ln(1 + \alpha x^{-\theta}) + 6\lambda\beta \ln(1 + \alpha x^{-\theta}) - 6\lambda\beta \ln(1 + \alpha x^{-\theta})\}$$

$$\log_e L_i = \{-(\theta + 1)(1 - p)\alpha\theta\beta\delta_i \ln x - (\beta + 1) + \alpha\theta \ln x + \beta \ln \lambda - 6 \ln \lambda - \alpha\theta \ln x + 12\lambda\beta^2 \alpha\theta \ln x + (1 - \delta_i) \ln(p + (1 - p)) + (1 - \delta_i)(1 - (1 - \lambda)) - (1 - p)\beta \alpha\theta \ln x + 6\lambda\beta \alpha\theta \ln x - 6\lambda\beta \alpha\theta \ln x\}$$

Simplifying

$$\log_e L_i = \{-(\theta + 1)(1 - p)[\alpha\theta\beta\delta_i \ln x - \beta - 1 + \alpha\theta \ln x + \beta \ln \lambda - 6 \ln \lambda - \alpha\theta \ln x + 12\lambda\beta^2 \alpha\theta \ln x + (1 - \delta_i) \ln(p + (1 - p)) + (1 - \delta_i)(1 - (1 - \lambda)) - (1 - p)\beta \alpha\theta \ln x + 6\lambda\beta \alpha\theta \ln x - 6\lambda\beta \alpha\theta \ln x]\} \quad (5)$$

Differentiate with respect to the parameters and equating the result to zero:

$$\frac{d \log_e L_i}{d\beta} = -(\theta + 1)(1 - p)\alpha\theta\delta_i \ln x - 1 + \ln \lambda + 24\lambda\beta\alpha\theta \ln x - (1 - p)\alpha\theta \ln x + 6\lambda\alpha\theta \ln x - 6\lambda\alpha\theta \ln x \quad (6)$$

$$\frac{d \log_e L_i}{d\alpha} = \{-(\theta + 1)(1 - p)\theta\beta\delta_i \ln x - \theta \ln x - \theta \ln x + 12\lambda\beta^2 \theta \ln x - (1 - p)\beta \theta \ln x + 6\lambda\beta \theta \ln x - 6\lambda\beta \theta \ln x\} \quad (7)$$

$$\frac{d \log_e L_i}{d\theta} = 2\alpha\theta\beta\delta_i \ln x - 2\alpha\theta p\beta\delta_i \ln x + \alpha\beta\delta_i \ln x - \alpha\beta p\delta_i \ln x + 12\lambda\beta^2 \alpha \ln x - (1 - p)\beta \alpha \ln x + 6\lambda\beta \alpha \ln x - 6\lambda\beta \alpha \ln x \quad (8)$$

$$\frac{d \log_e L_i}{d\lambda} = \frac{\beta}{\lambda} - \frac{6}{\lambda} \quad (9)$$

Equating(6), (7), (8) and (9) to 0 and simplifying to yield the results for the parameters.

$$\beta = \frac{1}{24} \frac{1}{\lambda \alpha \theta \ln x} (\alpha\theta\delta_i \ln x \theta (1 - p) + \alpha\theta\delta_i \ln x + 1 - \ln \lambda + \alpha\theta \ln x - \alpha\theta \ln x p) \quad (10)$$

$$\alpha = \frac{1}{\theta x} \{[-(\theta(1 - p) + 1)\theta\beta\delta_i \ln x - 2\theta \ln x + 12\lambda\beta^2 \theta \ln x - (1 - p)\beta \theta \ln x] \delta_i p\} \quad (11)$$

$$\theta = \frac{(\delta_i(1-p))}{\left\{ \alpha \left[\frac{-2\theta\beta\delta_i \ln x + 2\theta p\beta\delta_i \ln x - \beta\delta_i \ln x + \beta p\delta_i \ln x}{12\lambda\beta^2 \theta \ln x + \beta \ln x - \beta \ln x p - 12\lambda\beta \ln x} \right] \right\}} \quad (12)$$

$$\lambda = \frac{\beta - 6}{\delta_i - 1} \quad (13)$$

Data Set: Survival Times of Patients Suffering from Head and Neck Cancer

This data is a real data set represents the survival times of a group of patients suffering from head and neck cancer diseases and treated using a combination of radiotherapy and chemotherapy (RT+CT) [6]. The observations are as follows

:12.20, 23.56, 23.74, 25.87, 31.98, 37, 41.35, 47.38, 55.46, 58.36, 63.47, 68.46, 78.26, 74.47, 81.43, 84, 92, 94, 110, 112, 119, 127, 130, 133, 140, 146, 155, 159, 173, 179, 194, 195, 209, 249, 281, 319, 339, 432, 469, 519, 633, 725, 817, 1776.

RESULTS

Table 1: Summary Statistics for the Real Life Dataset

Parameter s	N	Minimum	Q_1	Median	Q_3	Mean	Maximum	Variance	Skewness	Kurtosis
Values	44	12.20	67.21	128.5	219.0	223.48	1776.00	93286.4	3.38382	13.5596

Table 2: Maximum Likelihood Parameter Estimates for the Real Life Dataset

Distribution	$\hat{\alpha}$	$\hat{\theta}$	$\hat{\beta}$	$\hat{\lambda}$
CTDD	7.1332450	0.8325806	5.2729666	0.9529972
TDD	8.3360370	0.7940678	7.1047256	0.9977101
DD	8.3795318	0.9459534	8.2395056	-

Table 3: The statistics ℓ , CAIC, and BIC for dataset

Distribution	$\hat{\ell}$	CAIC	BIC	Ranks
CTDD	277.7591	564.5438	570.6549	1 st
TDD	277.9416	564.9088	571.02	2 st
DD	279.7574	566.1148	570.8674	3 rd

Table 4: The A^* , W^* , K-S statistic and P-values for dataset

Distribution	A^*	W^*	K-S	Ranks
CTDD	0.1484659	0.02907137	0.064257	1 st
TDD	0.1917635	0.02226098	0.084235	2 nd
DD	0.2791308	0.04395533	0.09919	3 rd

DISCUSSION

In an attempt to use the real dataset, a real life data were used, which is called a dataset and is the survival times of a group of patients suffering from head and neck cancer diseases and treated using a combination of radiotherapy and chemotherapy (RT+CT). Table 1 is the summary statistics for the real life dataset, Table 2 is the maximum likelihood estimates of parameters for the real life dataset and Table 3, is the comparison test of the cubic transmuted Dagum distribution, transmuted dagum distribution and Dagum distribution using CAIC and BIC, where is it found that the cubic transmuted Dagum distribution fits the cure model better than the transmuted Dagum distribution and Dagum distribution. Table 4 is the test using the Anderson-Darling test statistic, the Kendall's test and the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test where it also shows that the cubic transmuted Dagum distribution is better to the other models.

Figure 1 is the histogram and plots of the pdf's for the dataset, Figure 2 is the histogram and plots of the estimated cdfs for the dataset, while Figure 3, Figure 4 and figure 5 are the probability plots for the fits of the cubic transmuted Dagum distribution, transmuted Dagum distribution and Dagum

distribution. The comparison shows an improvement on the existing models for use in cure rate analysis.

Figure1 Histogram and plots of the estimated Pdfs for dataset

Figure 2 Histogram and plots of the estimated Cdfs for Dataset

Figure 3 Probability plots for the fit of the cubic transmuted Dagum distribution on dataset

Figure 4 Probability plots for the fit of the transmuted Dagum distribution on dataset.

Figure 5 Probability plots for the fit of the Dagum distribution on dataset I.

CONCLUSION

This work is aimed at exploring new idea on using different probability distribution to for cur model and attempt to explore on transforming probability distribution on the existing cure models. It is hoped that there exist a cure model that fits better than the existing cure rate model. Therefore, it is recommended that a various transformation of different probability distribution to fit cure rate model to be done by other researchers for exploration and contribution to field of survival analysis. Based on this research work, it is recommended that more work to be extended to other distributions, by adding a parameter that makes work more flexible and to be compared with parents distributions for improvement and contributions to the knowledge of survival analysis.

Based on the real data set analysis, it can be concluded that Dagum distribution can be useful in cure model and real life analysis. The differences in the transmuted form of the Dagum distribution, and cubic form of the distribution have similar characteristics, eventhough the cubic tranmuted form fits more better, and when a data set has a multimodal effects, the cubic tranmuted form is more appropriate than the Transmuted form of the distribution.

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CONFLICT OF INTERESTS

No conflict of interest.

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